

Matsayin Mace A Kirarin Hausa

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Gabatarwa

Zantukan hikima ɓangare ne na adabin Hausa wanda ya haɗa da karin magana da kirari da salon magana da kacici kacici da sauransu da ake watsawa a tsakanin al'umma tun kaka da kakani. Fagen zantukan hikima, fage ne da za a iya amfani da shi domin gano alakar da ke tsakanin tunanin al'umma da adabinsu.

Kasancewar kirari da Karin magana nau'oi ne na zantukan hikima waɗanda suka shafi adabi, ya sa wannan aiki ya kasance an yi amfani da adabi a matsayin ma'auna na falsafar Hausawa. Domin haka, a wannan bincike, an yi nazarin kirari ne a matsayin falsafar Bahaushe game da mata.

Zantukan Hikima

Samuwar zantukan hikima shi ya haifar da rubutu, haka kuma tasirin addinin musulunci ya kawo samuwar rubutu a Hausa da malamai suka yi la'akari da tsarin zantukan hikima ga al'umma sai suka yi tunanin amfani da rubutu domin zayyana zantukan hikima domin jawo hankalin mutane zuwa ga koyarwar addinin musulunci. Hausawa sun dauki zantukan hikima a matsayin ma'aunin gurbin gaskiya, kasancewar yadda suke furshe a cikin al'adu da ɗabi'un mutane waɗanda suke nuni da hoton wannan al'umma, irin su almara da tastuniya da hikaya da karin magana da sauransu. (Funiss, 1996 da Shu'aibu, 2003 da Azima, 2011).

Matsayin Mace a Warin Bahaushe

Al'ummar Hausawa sun ba mata matsayin masu kula da gidajensu, irin matsayi na masu kula da 'ya 'ya da sna'o'I irin su saƙa da ginin tukwanne na dafa abinci da kiwon ƙananan dabbobi a cikin gidajen su. Magaji, 1999 yayin da yake sharhi a kan matsayin mace musamman ta fuskar kishi, ya bayyana yadda mace a saboda kishi ta kan yi ƙiyayya ko soyayya domin kishi.

Matan Hausawa sun siffantu da wasu halaye da ɗabi'u wasu masu kyau tun da can har zuwa yanzu ɗaya daga cikin irin waɗanda addini da al'adu suka yi na'am da su, sannan akwai waɗanda suke abin ƙi. Daga cikin masu kyau akwai irin su kunya da hakuri da makamantan su. Daga cikin irin halaye da ɗabi'u na ƙi kuwa akwai irin su karuwanci da rashin kunya da gulma da makamantan su. Balbasatu (2008).

A taƙaice mace tana da matsayi a wurin Bahaushe musamman in aka kwatanta da matsayin mace a wurin wasu al'ummu, a wajen Bahaushe mace a ba ce mai daraja matsayin ta na matar gida mai kula da duk al'ummar cikin gida kuma mai alfarma ce mai daraja mazaje sun dauki mata a matsayin masu rauni da kaskanci da rashin basira da nuna kishi, gasu magulmanta gasu kuma karuwai, sanna ba a dauki ilimantar dasu a matsayin abu mai muhimmanci ba waɗannan bayanai ya nuna matar Bahaushe da irin matsayin ta, yadda mace takan kasance ba a halicce ta don komai ba face sai don bautar

aure, da yi wa namiji biyayya da yi masa hidima (Balbasatu 1995) da waƙannan bayanai za mu fahimci irin matsayin mace a wurin Bahausha ta fuskar kula da gida ta fuskar dafa abinci da renon yara da kuma halin kunya. Haka kuma akan koyar da mata sana'oi irin waƙanda za su rika yi a gidajen su kamar kaƙi da saƙa da duk sauran sana'oi domin neman ruƙin asiri. Da kuma wasu halaye da akan danganta mace da su, kuma irin su kishi da karuwanci waƙanda halaye ne abin ki, da haka ya nuna yadda irin wannan matsayin ya fito fili a cikin zantukan hikima na Hausawa.

Mace a Kirari

Kirari a Hausa wasu kalmoni ne na kambamawa da ke zuwa a siffanta mutum ko wani abu a kan shahararren karfi ko daraja ko alƙarfi (Kafin Hausa 1985; Gusau 1984; Garba 1998). Dangane da matsayin da mace take da shi a idon Bahausha a kwai kirari da suke nuna ko fito da muhimmancin mace ko kambama ta, wadda tamkar ana nuna girman ta. A wannan maƙala, an karkasa kirarin mata zuwa rukuni-rukuni. Akwai kirari da suka shafi manyan mata da 'yan mata da waƙanda suka shafi zamantakewar musamman na matan aure da amare da zawa. An kuma duba wani ɓangare na kirarin da ak yi wa matan da suka fanda wa sanannun tsarin zamantakewar al'ummar Hausawa wato Karuwai.

A kan yi wa mata kirari da:

- Uwa ta fi Uba ko da uban Sarki ne
- Mata agogon bango ku juya yadda kuke so
- Uwa ma ba da mama
- Mata na inna dangin yumɓu
- Mata iyayen gida, in ba ku ba gida, in kun yi yawa gida ya ɓaci
- Mata ba tukwane ba, belle a kwankwasa a ji wacce ta fi kwari
- Mata mugun abu nama ya kashe ɗan kura
- Mata kuɗi suke so ba farin ido ba

Duk waƙannan kirari ne waƙanda suka fito da matsayin mace karara dangane da irin halayen ta, ko muhimmancinta da ɗaukakar ta a cikin al'ummar Hausawa. Komin matsayin mutum ko daraja ko muƙami ko matsayi ko kuɗi a cikin al'umma yana farkashi ko yin biyayya ne ga mace musamman uwa ko mata.

Kirarin 'yan mata

'Yan mata ana nufin 'ya mace wacce ta wuce yarinya ta fara shiga zangon manya. Akan yi wa 'yan mata kirari da:

- 'yan mata adon gari
- 'yan matan aljanna masu kayan kallo
- Hoda abin adon 'yan mata
- Bosara karya gado
- Yarinya goro sa samari noma
- Zinariya abar wasoso

Kirarin matan aure

Aure hanya ce ta kulla zaman tare tsakanin namiji da mace ba tare da iyakancewa ba sai dai in mutuwa ta raba, wanda ake tabbatarwa ta amincewar ma'auratan da

waliyansu da kafa shaidu. (Yakasai 2012). Bahaushen ya kan yi aure fiye da mace daya wato daga daya zuwa mata hudu.

Akan yi wa uwargida kirari kamar haka:

- Uwargida sarautar mata
- Uwargida ran gida
- Uwargida tankarin gida
- Uwargida tana tuwo tana sadakar loma
- A ci yau, a ci gobe sai abincin uwargida
- Tuwon uwargida a ki ci, a kwana da yunwa
- Kwari mai kwara miya, wataran sai ta kwara tsiyarta

Kirarin Amarya

Amarya ita ce matar da aka auro ta sabuwa, ko kuma ita ce karamar matar gida. Daga cikin al'adun Hausawa dangane da zaman iyali duk lokacin da namiji ya auri mace sabuwa yakan yi doki sosai ta hanyar nuna soyayya da doki tamkar ba a sake auro wata matar ba, irin wannan yakan haifar da rashin zaman lafiya a gida musamman idan akwai wasu matan. Akan yi wa amarya kirari kamar haka:

- Amarya ba kya laifi ko kin kashe dan masu gida
- Amarsu ta ango
- Amarya sha gudɗa
- Amarya mai maganar siga
- Amarya in bata hau doki ba, ba a aza mata kaya ba

A wannan kirarin duk yana nuna irin matsayin amarya ce, kamar so da kauna da daraja ko kimar ta kasancewar ta amarya.

Kirarin Zawarawa

Bazawara ita ce matar da ta yi aure kuma aka sake ta, ko auren ta ya mutu. (Sarkin Sudan 2012). Ita bazawara takan yi zama na zawarci wato kafin ta samu miji ta yi wani auren, a dalilin wannan zama ko halin da takan kasance na zawarci sai da aka samu wasu halaye ko yanayi waɗanda ake danganta bazawara da su. kamar haka;

- Bazawara uwar son banza, ana baki kina hangen na aljihu
- Ba'a koya wa bazawara lullubi
- In ka ga godiya da Sirdi, wani ta kayar.

Kirarin Karuwai

Kirarin da akan yi wa karuwai akasari kirari ne da akan fito da munanan halayensu, a wani lokaci kirari kan fito a matsayin zambo saboda munin abin da suke yi. Misali Bahaushen kan yi wa karuwa kirari don ya nuna halayenta kamar haka:

- Karuwa 'yar mamman da Alu
- Marina don jagwalgwale aka yi ki
- Kwaryar alewa ba kya gamawa lafiya
- Ke ce tunku da kararawa ma ja dangi bala'i
- Kin yi gamon dangi, dangi ba su yi gamon ki ba
- Karuwa kwata ce, ba ta tarar nagari, da kare da jaki da doki duk nata ne

Wadannan kirari duk zambo ne dangane da wadannan munanan halayenta abin ki. Kuma tamkar ana nuna rashin kyan wannan halaye ne. Ma'ana mai mummunar dabi'a wadda addini da al'ada suka kyamata.

Kammalawa

A karshe, nazartar kirarin Hausa ya bayyana irin matsayin mace a wurin Bahaushe, kamar yadda haka ya fito a cikin adabin sa musamman kirari. An fito da irin muhimmancin mace da kuma daraja da kima da daukakar ta. Misali akan yi wasu kirari don nuna matsayin mace ya fi na namiji muhimmancin ko kuma in babu mace ba gida, yadda akan ce “uwa ta fi uba, ko da uban sarki ne”. Haka kuma wasu kirarin da aka nazarta sun nuna siffa da shiga na ‘yan mata da kwalliya da nuna launin mata.

Har ila yau a nazarin da aka yi an gano yadda kirari ya fito da rauni ko wasu halaye da ke kawo wa mace rashin daraja a cikin al'umma, kamar dabi'ar karuwanci. Kamar karuwancin ana nuna rashin kimar ta da daraja a cikin al'umma kusan ana nuna munin wannan dabi'ar da hani da shiga cikin ta. Daga karshe wannan mahangar ta nuna yanayin tunanin Bahaushe da falsafarsa game da mace, mun ga haka a daya daga cikin zantukan hikima na Hausa musamman kirari.

Manazarta

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